

Quantification of water fluxes and soil water balance in agricultural fields under different tillage and irrigation systems using water stable isotopes

Alba Canet-Martí^{a,*}, Angela Morales-Santos^b, Reinhard Nolz^b, Guenter Langergraber^a, Christine Stumpp^b

^a University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Department of Water, Atmosphere and Environment, Institute for Sanitary Engineering and Water Pollution Control (SIG), Muthgasse 18, Vienna 1190, Austria

^b University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Department of Water, Atmosphere and Environment, Institute for Soil Physics and Rural Water Management (SoPhy), Muthgasse 18, Vienna 1190, Austria

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable agriculture should be based on management practices that improve resource usage efficiency and minimize harmful impacts on the environment while maintaining and stabilizing crop production. Both tillage and irrigation can have an influence on water resource usage and thus on hydrological processes within agroecosystems. However, it remains difficult to directly assess the effect of practices on water fluxes. Therefore, the objective of the study was to use oxygen and hydrogen isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) in the pore water of soil profiles as well as moisture contents for quantifying the soil water balance and fluxes. Covering all combinations, water content and isotope analysis in soil profiles were performed for 16 plots planted with winter wheat and managed with different tillage (conventional tillage (CT), reduced tillage (RT), minimal tillage (MT), and no-tillage (NT)) and irrigation systems (hose reel boom irrigation with nozzles (BI), sprinkler irrigation (SI), drip irrigation (DI) and no irrigation (NI)). The results indicated that the more intense the tillage, the lower the water content. Among the irrigation systems, DI had the highest average water content. Tracing the isotope minimum of winter precipitation in pore water of soil profiles showed deeper percolation of water in the CT plots, which indicates higher water flow velocity for CT compared to other tillage variants. Considering both water content and water flow velocities resulted in average water fluxes ranging from 23 to 46 mm for six months (end of November to May). For the same time period, between 80% and 91% of the water contributed to evapotranspiration. The resulting evapotranspiration within tillage and irrigation variants decreased in the order CT>RT>MT>NT and SI>BI>DI>NI. Thus, the method revealed that the lower water content in CT fields is a consequence of both deeper water infiltration and higher evapotranspiration. Moreover, irrigation water contributed mostly to evapotranspiration, and drip irrigation showed the lowest evapotranspiration among irrigation systems. This study demonstrated that water stable isotopes can be used as indicators and are a promising method to quantify average water fluxes in agricultural fields with great potential for evaluating management practices.

1. Introduction

Sustainable agriculture should be based on management practices that improve resource usage efficiency and minimize harmful impacts on the environment while maintaining and stabilizing crop production (Hobbs et al., 2008). Sustainable soil management has the potential to enhance soil physical conditions for plant growth considerably, including adequate availability of water, nutrients, and air in the rooting zone (Blume and van Meerveld, 2015; Hartge and Horn, 2016). Soil

management includes, for example, depth, intensity, frequency, and equipment of tillage operations, as well as prospective planning crop rotations (Hatfield and Sauer, 2011; Jian et al., 2020; Page et al., 2020). Additionally, irrigation might become necessary under certain conditions to maintain the crop yield and achieve food security (Mueller et al., 2012; Steduto et al., 2009). Understanding the influence of tillage and irrigation on hydrological processes in agroecosystems is crucial for decision-making. However, the direct impact of these management practices on soil hydrological fluxes is difficult to quantify.

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: alba.canet@boku.ac.at (A. Canet-Martí).

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Soil tillage modifies the soil structure and its pore system (Buczko et al., 2006; Pires et al., 2017). The impact of tillage on soil structure depends on the intensity and variants of tillage, soil type and climate (Strudley et al., 2008). Common tillage practices range from conventional tillage (CT) to conservation tillage practices, including reduced (RT) or minimal tillage (MT), and no-tillage (NT). CT consists of plowing the topsoil to a depth of about 30 cm, which increases macropores and, thus, infiltration rates (Strudley et al., 2008). Some adverse effects of soils under CT are the compaction of deeper layers and soil erosion (Birkas et al., 2004; Lipiec et al., 2006). These effects have led to a decrease in tillage intensity in recent years, shifting to no-tillage or conservation tillage practices (Hobbs et al., 2008). Within NW Europe, NT is generally associated with greater macropore connectivity but smaller pores compared to tilled fields, resulting in lower infiltration rates and lower soil hydraulic conductivity (Mueller et al., 2009; Pires et al., 2017; Skaalsveen et al., 2019; Strudley et al., 2008). Reduced or minimum tillage plots tend to have intermediate characteristics (Kreiselmeier et al., 2020; Schwen et al., 2011). Changes in soil structure and soil hydraulic characteristics can vary over time. For example, CT soils tend to decrease infiltration rate over time after plowing due to soil re-aggregation (Schwartz et al., 2010). The high temporal dynamics of agricultural systems makes it costly to monitor and compare different management practices (Alletto et al., 2015; Kreiselmeier et al., 2020; Schwen et al., 2011; Strudley et al., 2008). Hence, integrative methods to quantify water fluxes would be of great help to actually investigate the effects of different tillage systems.

The efficient use of irrigation water is crucial to promote sustainable agricultural production and sustainable water management (Mueller et al., 2012; Unver et al., 2017). High efficiency can be achieved by effectively managing irrigation using a water-efficient irrigation system (Unver et al., 2017). Efficient irrigation technologies include drip irrigation and sprinkler irrigation systems. On the one hand, drip irrigation (DI) is a low-intensity irrigation system considered efficient in terms of evaporation losses. It is designed to dose the irrigation water, ensuring certain soil moisture in the root zone so that the irrigation water is well distributed vertically and laterally in the soil, and evaporation losses are reduced (Bajpai and Kaushal, 2020; Subbaiah, 2013). Sprinkler irrigation systems, such as overhead sprinkler nozzles (SI) or a moving platform with hose reel boom with nozzles (BI), distribute water as spray droplets simulating rainfall. In overhead sprinklers, irrigation water is unevenly distributed and evaporation losses are higher than in drip irrigation, as they are affected by canopy interception and evaporation (Cavero et al., 2009; Jagermeyr et al., 2015; Uddin and Murphy, 2020). Boom irrigation systems are high-intensity irrigation systems designed for homogeneous distribution, and it is assumed that water infiltrates into the soil with little losses compared to center pivot sprinkler systems (Nakawuka et al., 2014). The differences in the evaporation and drift losses of irrigation systems with nozzles or sprinklers are mainly related to weather variables and equipment-related factors such as droplet size or pressure (McLean et al., 2000; Uddin and Murphy, 2020). In any case, irrigation water increases the water available for evapotranspiration, contributes to water soil storage and, depending on the irrigation system and amount, also to percolation and surface or lateral runoff (Jagermeyr et al., 2015).

Studying the combined effect of tillage and irrigation systems can help to understand the actual impact of different management practices on soil water status and changes in hydrological processes. It still remains a challenge to quantify the impact of different management practices on soil water fluxes in agricultural soils. Currently, quantification of water flux in the unsaturated zone is done by indirect methods such as process-based models. Complex soil hydrological models are calibrated to long-term in-situ measurements, such as water contents and/or matric potential, or simulations are performed using information of soil hydraulic properties from pedotransfer functions or laboratory analysis. Other methods include recharge estimates from tracer approaches at the field scale (de Vries and Simmers, 2002). The latter are

simpler and allow direct quantification.

Tracers can provide integrative information on the origin and transport of the water in the soil (Groh et al., 2018; Mueller et al., 2014; Sprenger et al., 2019). The ratio of stable oxygen and hydrogen isotopes of water ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) in precipitation, for example, can be used as an environmental tracer. The isotopic composition of precipitation is modified by fractionation processes throughout the water cycle, mainly associated with phase change, e.g. evaporation, condensation, freezing (Craig, 1961; Dansgaard, 1964). This leads to seasonal variations in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ of precipitation water. The seasonal variations may still be observed in the pore water of soils, with a time lag and an attenuation of the signal depending on transport processes (Groh et al., 2018; Koenerger et al., 2016; Mueller et al., 2014; Sprenger et al., 2019; Stumpp et al., 2018). Therefore, it is possible to link the isotopic composition measured in pore water throughout a soil depth profile at a given time with a period determined by the isotopic composition of past precipitation events. In combination with soil water content data, water fluxes can be quantified (Barbecot et al., 2018; Chesnaux and Stumpp, 2018). A simple method to do so is the peak-shift method, a space for time concept based on the displacement of a tracer peak to directly quantify the water fluxes in the soil. Once the soil water flux is known, we can estimate other fluxes, such as evapotranspiration, using a water balance approach (Boumaiza et al., 2020, 2021b), or it can even be used to split evaporation and transpiration processes (Liebhard et al., 2022). In their study, Chesnaux and Stumpp (2018) highlighted the potential of the method to quantify average water fluxes in deep, homogeneous sedimentary soils. In agricultural soils, water stable isotopes have been used to assess nitrate leaching (Sprenger et al., 2016a), glyphosate leaching (Schlögl et al., 2022) and the effects of different management practices, irrigation systems and crops on evaporation processes (Al-Oqaili et al., 2020; Busari et al., 2013; Mahindawansa et al., 2020).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the suitability of the peak-shift method to quantify the soil water balance and fluxes in agricultural fields impacted by tillage and irrigation practices. The tillage variants considered were conventional tillage, reduced tillage, minimal tillage and no-tillage, and the irrigation systems were boom irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, drip irrigation and no irrigation. We estimated average evapotranspiration by considering soil water flux as mobile soil water in the soil water balance. We then evaluated if there were significant differences in mobile soil water and evapotranspiration between the treatments. Finally, we discussed the applicability and the limitations of the method for studying the impact of management practices.

2. Materials and methods

Soil hydraulic properties and the isotopic composition of the soil water of sixteen profiles were analyzed, covering all combinations of four tillage variants and four irrigation systems. We used the peak-shift method (see Section 2.6.1. for more details) and a water balance approach to quantify mobile soil water and evapotranspiration representative for the time period identified by the isotopic composition of pore water in the soil profiles.

2.1. Experimental site

The experimental site was located in Obersiebenbrunn, in Lower Austria, ca. 35 km east of Vienna. According to the Köppen-Geiger classification (Kottek et al., 2006), the climate is warm-temperate. Annual average precipitation, air temperature and potential evapotranspiration (ET_0) were 540 mm, 10.5 °C, and 626 mm, respectively, according to the Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik (ZAMG). The experimental site belonged to the Agricultural School of Obersiebenbrunn (Landwirtschaftliche Fachschule, LFS), and it was managed together with the University of Natural Resources and Life Science (BOKU) for research and for training farmers in irrigation practices (Morales-Santos and Nolz, 2023).

Precipitation and temperature (Fig. 1), as well as relative humidity (RH) data, were collected from a weather station located at the LFS Obersiebenbrunn. Additional meteorological information (i.e., solar radiation (R_s) and wind speed (u_2)) was obtained from the Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik (ZAMG) weather station located in Groß-Enzersdorf (ca. 16 km south-west from the experimental site), which was used for calculating ET_0 (Fig. 1) using the Penman-Monteith equation (Allen et al., 1998). The crop coefficient approach was used to calculate the crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) assuming standard conditions, e.g. well-fertilized, disease-free crops, and optimal soil water conditions (Allen et al., 1998). At the time the samples were taken, winter wheat was planted, which has a maximum root depth between 1.5 and 1.8 m (Allen et al., 1998).

Monthly data of isotope ratios in precipitation (Fig. 1) and the Local Meteoric Water Line are available for the station Hohe Warte (30 km from the study site) in the database of the Global Network of Isotopes in Precipitation (GNIP) of the International Atomic Energy Agency (<http://www.iaea.org/services/networks/gnip>; accessed October 12, 2020). It is worth noting that in April 2020, low isotope ratios (-101.2‰) were associated with only little precipitation (9 mm).

2.2. Trial design

The field had a surface area of $120 \times 120 \text{ m}^2$ and it was divided into four irrigation areas and four tillage variants in three randomized replications (Fig. 2). The agricultural tillage practices compared were conventional tillage (CT) with disc harrow and plough to break and turn the soil, reduced tillage (RT) with disc harrow and disc cultivator to stir the soil before sowing, minimal tillage (MT) using only disc harrow, and no-tillage (NT) without soil disturbance. The irrigation systems implemented were boom irrigation (BI), consisting of a hose reel boom with nozzles, overhead sprinkler irrigation (SI), surface drip irrigation (DI), and no irrigation (NI). The crops planted in 2019 and 2020 were soy-bean and winter wheat. Information regarding tillage depths, irrigation dates and amounts, planting, and harvest dates can be found in Table 1. The amounts and timing of irrigation were made at the discretion of the

farmers based on the experience of previous years.

2.3. Soil characterization

According to the Austrian Soil Map, the soil was classified as Chernozem (<https://bodenkarte.at>; accessed March 22, 2023), with 4% of organic carbon content in the topsoil (Vadibeler et al., 2022). Two sampling campaigns were conducted to characterize the soil of the experimental field, where all tillage variants were covered. Samples were taken prior to the crop season in 2019 (see Table 1). An illustration of the sampling locations is shown in Fig. 2. Undisturbed samples were taken on March 27, 2019, from the topsoil (i.e., 5–15 cm depth) ($n = 35$) with stainless steel cylinders (200 cm^3), and their dry weight was determined to calculate soil dry bulk density (ρ_b). Undisturbed samples were also collected at depths of 20–60 cm ($n = 36$) and 60–90 cm ($n = 12$) at the boundaries of each plot to measure ρ_b . Mean and standard deviation of ρ_b were calculated by tillage variant and depth interval. On March 28, 2019, disturbed soil samples ($n = 64$) were collected from four depth intervals (0–15, 15–30, 30–60, and 60–90 cm) to determine the percentage of sand, silt and clay by combining the wet sieving method and pipette method using an automatic Kubiena apparatus. Based on the homogeneity observed in the soil layers throughout the field, the mean and standard deviation were calculated for each depth interval.

2.4. Soil core sampling for isotope and soil water content analysis

In order to apply the peak-shift method, we took soil core samples to analyze the profile distribution of oxygen and hydrogen isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) of pore water and soil water content. It is noteworthy to mention that no artificial tracers were added to the field and no isotopic labeling was done. The isotopic ratios of precipitation water were used as an environmental tracer to quantify the water flux in the soil.

For this study, we sampled one of the three replications to cover all combinations of tillage and irrigation variants (see Fig. 2). Adding another replication would have implied reducing the number of

Fig. 1. Temporal variation of a) daily air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and monthly values of $\delta^2\text{H}$ (●) and d-excess (x) in precipitation (‰); b) monthly precipitation (mm) and ET_0 (inverted histogram) (mm d $^{-1}$). The shaded area indicates the isotope minimum of winter precipitation. Values of $\delta^2\text{H}$ in precipitation from the station Hohe Warte, available in the Global Network of Isotopes in Precipitation (GNIP-IAEA) database.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the experimental field. The coloured plots indicate four tillage variants, of which there are three randomized replications. The four irrigation systems divide the site into four areas of different surface. The soil core samples (●) were taken on May 28 and 29, 2020, in one of the replications. For each soil profile, two individual soil core samples were taken in close proximity to obtain a composite sample. The crosses show where soil samples were taken to measure soil water content (SWC), water retention curve (WRC), and bulk density (ρ_b).

management practices covered by the study, as only a limited number of samples can be measured at the same time, which is important for the comparison of results relying on a reference date measurement approach.

The soil sampling campaign was performed on May 28 and 29, 2020, to collect samples for pore water isotope analysis. Covering all combinations, sixteen soil profiles were sampled (see Fig. 2). Even though soil texture was similar throughout the entire field, soil cores were taken from two soil profiles in each plot to obtain a composite sample. This was done to avoid sampling along preferential flow pathways and to obtain a more representative sample. The soil cores were taken down to 90 cm depth at 10 cm sub-sampling intervals using a hand auger, resulting in 144 samples altogether. The samples were disturbed and placed in Ziploc® bags, of which we used two for double-bagging to avoid leakages. After analyzing the isotopic composition of soil pore water, gravimetric water content was determined, and the volumetric water content was calculated considering bulk density. Soil water content was also continuously monitored at 20 cm depth in the field with Hydra Probe sensors (Stevens Water Monitoring Systems, Inc., Oregon, USA) to calculate soil water storage.

Water retention curves were generated from undisturbed soil samples ($n = 25$) using HYPROP (Hydraulic PROProperty analyser) and fitted to the van Genuchten (1980) model to estimate residual water content (θ_r). The samples were taken on March 27, 2019, from all tillage variants under DI at depths of 5–15, 15–30, 30–40, 40–60 and 60–80 cm, with

duplicates at the topsoil, the area of greatest variability (see Fig. 2).

2.5. Analysis of isotopic composition of soil water

The isotopic composition of soil water was analyzed from samples collected during the sampling campaign carried out on the 28th and 29th of May 2020. Prior to isotopic analysis, the bags were filled with dry air and equilibrated for three days to reach the liquid-vapour equilibrium within the bag (Wassenaar et al., 2008). Oxygen and hydrogen isotope ratios of the vapor samples were analyzed with a laser-based isotope analyzer (Picarro L2130-i). A two-point calibration was used with laboratory reference standards. Soil samples and samples with isotopic internal standard waters were prepared identically and the headspace analyzed for both water and soil samples according to established procedure described in Wassenaar et al. (2008) and Gralher et al. (2018). Between the internal standards, three soil samples were analyzed.

The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ of irrigation water were analyzed using a laser-based isotope analyzer (Picarro L2140-i). A two-point calibration with laboratory reference material calibrated against VSMOW-SLAP (Vienna Standard Mean Ocean Water-Standard Light Antarctic Precipitation) scale was used. Each sample was measured seven times. The isotope ratios were given in the δ notation in ‰ relative to the Vienna-Standard Mean Ocean Water (V-SMOW).

We calculated deuterium excess (d-excess) of global precipitation to

Table 1

Overview of the management practices and sampling campaigns at the experimental site.

Year	Date	Management practice	CT	RT	MT	NT
2018	31th Oct	Tillage Cultivator (12 cm)	●	●	●	
	12th Nov	Tillage Plough (30 cm)	●			
2019	4th Mar	Fertilizer Calcium-ammonium-nitrate (NAC) 154 kg/ha	●	●	●	●
	27th Mar	Sampling Undisturbed cylinders for WRC and ρ_b	●	●	●	●
	28th Mar	Sampling Disturbed samples for soil texture	●	●	●	●
	23th Apr	Tillage Cultivator (12 cm)		●		
	18th Apr	Fertilizer Calcium-ammonium-nitrate (NAC) 148 kg/ha	●	●	●	●
	7th May	Tillage Disc harrow (8 cm)	●	●	●	
	8th May	Planting Soybean variant Lenka	●	●	●	●
	11th May	Plant Roundup (4 l/ha)				●
	July-Aug	Irrigation DI:84 mm, SI:127 mm, BI:66 mm *	●	●	●	●
	3rd Oct	Harvest	●	●	●	●
	29th Oct	Tillage Disc harrow (8 cm)	●	●	●	
	29th Oct	Tillage Plough (30 cm)	●			
	29th Oct	Tillage Cultivator (12 cm)		●		
	30th Oct	Planting Winter wheat	●	●	●	●
	2020	9th Mar	Fertilizer Calcium-ammonium-nitrate (NAC) 220 kg/ha	●	●	●
28th Mar		Plant protection Type Broadway	●	●	●	●
16th Apr		Fertilizer Calcium-ammonium-nitrate (NAC) 220 kg/ha	●	●	●	●
22nd Apr		Irrigation DI: 27 mm, SI 48: mm, BI: 27 mm	●	●	●	●
20th May		Irrigation DI: 25 mm, SI: 25 mm, BI: 25 mm	●	●	●	●
28th May		Sampling Disturbed samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$	●		●	
29th May		Sampling Disturbed samples for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$		●		●
22th Jul		Harvest	●	●	●	●

CT: conventional tillage; RT: reduced tillage; MT: minimal tillage; NT: no-till
BI: hose reel boom with nozzles; SI: sprinkler irrigation; DI: drip irrigation; NI: non-irrigated area

WRC: Water Retention Curve

* total irrigation amount applied during different irrigation events occurring between 03/07/2019 and 03/08/2019.

identify the impact of fractionation in soil pore water due to evaporation, defined as: $d\text{-excess} = \delta^2\text{H} - 8 \cdot \delta^{18}\text{O}$. During evaporation, isotopes with lower atomic weight (i.e. lighter isotopes) are more prone to move into the gas phase. That way, when part of soil pore water evaporates, the remaining water is enriched in heavy isotopes. Soil water partially evaporated will have stable isotopes distributed along a line with a lower slope than precipitation water when displayed in a dual-isotope plot (e.g. in Fig. 3). This difference would result in d-excess values lower compared to the local precipitation average d-excess value.

2.6. Isotopic composition correction

An adjustment was made in order to minimize the inaccuracies that may occur in silty soils with low water content when using the direct liquid-vapor equilibration method for porewater isotope analysis (Gralher et al., 2021; Vadibeler et al., 2022). As many samples had to be analysed, samples were stored in the fridge for up to 28 days. Even though this does not necessarily have an impact on the isotopes ratios in pore water of double-bagged soils samples where isotope enrichment was observed after 6 months, an analysis within 10–15 days is still recommended to avoid any effects due to water losses and fractionation (Hendry et al., 2015). For the adjustment, the same soil was used and dried in the oven for 48 h. Three replicates of oven-dried soil samples of approximately 50 g (the average amount of soil in the original samples) were spiked with 1, 2, 3, and 5 g of isotopic reference water. The samples were analyzed after three, nine and thirty days following the same procedure as for the soil core samples (see Section 2.3). A multiple regression analysis was performed in order to determine the relationship between the difference in oxygen and hydrogen isotope ratios ($\Delta\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\Delta\delta^2\text{H}$ values), the gravimetric water content and the time between sample preparation and analysis of isotopic composition. The regression equation was used to correct the isotopic composition of the soil samples according to their water content and the time elapsed.

2.7. Water flux quantification

2.7.1. Peak-shift method: Mobile soil water

Water flux (q) [$\text{L} \cdot \text{T}^{-1}$] was quantified using the peak-shift method (Chesnaux and Stumpp, 2018; Leibundgut et al., 2009; Saxena and Dressdie, 1983). As a simplification, the method assumes piston flow with a predominance of the convective transport of water flow downwards in the soil profile. It is a simple method to quantify average water fluxes by identifying the seasonal isotope distribution in the pore water for back-tracing precipitation events. For example, precipitation significantly enriched or depleted in heavy isotopes would indicate a summer peak or winter nadir, respectively.

The period T was defined by the difference between the sampling date (i.e., here, end of May 2020) and the date of a prominent isotope signal in precipitation. For our study, the most prominent nadir with a substantial amount of precipitation was identified for November 2019 (Fig. 1). This nadir was found at different depths in each profile. The difference was attributed to the management practices, the only factor that differed between the plots.

The water flux represents the volume of water flowing through a section of the porous media per unit time:

$$q = \theta \cdot v \quad (1)$$

$$v = \frac{z_{i+T} - z_i}{T} \quad (2)$$

where θ [-] is the volumetric water content, and v is the water flow velocity defined by the depth identified at the beginning (z_i) and at the end (z_{i+T}) [L] of the period T [T]. The beginning of the period refers to November 2019, i.e. the nadir of isotope ratios in precipitation, and the end to the sampling date, i.e. end of May 2020.

Assuming that residual (immobile) water content does not contribute to water flux, q can be calculated by integrating the difference between volumetric water content (θ_w) [-] and the residual water content (θ_r) [-] over a depth interval within the unsaturated zone (dz) [L] in the period T :

$$q_{(z,T)} = \frac{1}{T} \int_{z_i}^{z_{i+T}} (\theta_w - \theta_r) \cdot dz \quad (3)$$

In this study, we adapted Eq. (3) to quantify mobile soil water $D_{(T)}$ [L] as a term of the water balance equation, in mm:

Fig. 3. Dual-isotope ($\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) plot of soil water samples, irrigation water from the experimental field, and the Local Meteoric Water Line (LMWL) corresponding to Hohe Warte, Vienna (GNIP-IAEA); the blue color range indicates the depth at which the samples were taken.

$$D_{(T)} = \sum_{i=0}^m (\theta_w - \theta_r)(z_{i+1} - z_i) \quad (4)$$

Using Eq [4] we calculated the available water at each sub-sampling interval ($z_{i+1} - z_i$) [L], from the top surface until m intervals to the depth of interest, i.e. the winter isotope minimum found in pore water.

2.8. Soil water balance: Evapotranspiration

The water balance approach was used to estimate evapotranspiration for each plot and over the same period. The water balance was calculated for the period T , which was the same as that used for the peak-shift method (i.e., Nov 2019 – May 2020). The evapotranspiration ($ET_{(T)}$) cumulated during T was quantified for each profile by using the water balance equation:

$$ET_{(T)} = Irr_{(T)} + P_{(T)} - \Delta S_{(T)} - D_{(T)} \quad (5)$$

where $Irr_{(T)}$ stands for irrigation water added during the same period, and $P_{(T)}$ is the accumulated, measured precipitation during T . Soil storage ($\Delta S_{(T)}$) corresponds to the difference between the soil water content at the end and at the beginning of the period T determined with the Hydra Probe sensors at 20 cm depth (see Section 2.2 for more details).

We neglected both lateral surface and subsurface runoff due to the imperceptible slope and the soil homogeneity. $D_{(T)}$ would be equivalent to the term groundwater recharge or percolation in the water balance equation. However, it could not be referred to as such because it was calculated in the root zone and could still be taken up by plants or evaporated in the first few centimeters of soil. It would potentially become groundwater recharge if the water exceeds the depth of the root system and no further upward fluxes occur. All terms were expressed in mm.

2.9. Statistical analysis

We performed pairwise t-tests to determine if there was a statistically significant difference in (a) mobile soil water and (b) evapotranspiration for the different groups concerning (1) tillage and (2) irrigation. The parameter values of each subgroup of 1 and 2 were compared to the parameter values from all other groups. By this means, we obtained p-values in both parameters and all four subgroups.

3. Results

3.1. Soil properties

The soil texture was homogeneous within the specific soil depths for all the tillage variants, and the sand portion increased abruptly at 60–90 cm depth, shifting from silty loam texture to loam to sandy loam (see Table 2). The topsoil bulk density (0–15 cm) was significantly greater in the untilled plots compared to tilled plots (see Table 3); however, it increased with depth in the CT and RT plots, while the opposite occurred in the deepest layer (60–90 cm) of the MT and NT plots. The θ_r ranged from 0.050 to 0.097 $\text{cm}^3 / \text{cm}^3$ depending on tillage variant and depth. Water content in the topsoil (20 cm) measured in November 2019 and May 2020 and used to calculate $\Delta S_{(T)}$ was 0.30 ± 0.05 and $0.16 \pm 0.01 \text{ cm}^3 / \text{cm}^3$.

3.2. Measured soil water content and isotopes in the soil profiles

The dual-isotope diagram for $\delta^2\text{H} - \delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the soil pore water is shown in Fig. 3. The equation of the regression line was $\delta^2\text{H} = 5.78 \delta^{18}\text{O} - 14.12$ ($R^2 = 0.94$). This slope was lower compared to the slope of the LMWL for Vienna ($\delta^2\text{H} = 7.47 \delta^{18}\text{O} + 2.22$), indicating the relevance of isotope fractionation processes due to evaporation in the topsoil. Irrigation water had an isotopic composition of $\delta^{18}\text{O} = -9.92\text{‰}$, and $\delta^2\text{H} = -72.0\text{‰}$, and it came from local groundwater. The ratios were similar

Table 2

Mean and standard deviation of soil particle size and soil texture at different soil depths.

Sample depth (cm)	n	Clay	Silt	Sand	USDA Soil texture classification
		< 2 μm (%)	63–2 μm (%)	2000–63 μm (%)	
0–15	16	14.39 ± 2.40	56.91 ± 3.33	28.70 ± 2.58	Silty Loam
15–30	16	17.38 ± 3.31	54.54 ± 3.75	28.07 ± 3.83	Silty Loam
30–60	16	19.67 ± 2.52	51.93 ± 3.08	28.37 ± 4.09	Silty Loam
60–90	16	11.00 ± 4.27	42.49 ± 11.28	46.50 ± 12.30	Loam to Sandy loam

n = Number of samples

Table 3

Mean and standard deviation of bulk density at different soil depths in different tillage variants.

	Bulk density, ρ_b (g/cm ³)		
	depth intervals		
Tillage variant	5–15 cm	20–60 cm	60–90 cm
Conventional tillage	1.27 ± 0.05 (9)	1.49 ± 0.05 (9)	1.41 ± 0.01 (3)
Reduced tillage	1.23 ± 0.09 (8)	1.47 ± 0.07 (9)	1.49 ± 0.03 (3)
Minimal tillage	1.21 ± 0.06 (9)	1.41 ± 0.14 (9)	1.19 ± 0.03 (3)
No tillage	1.48 ± 0.05 (9) *	1.50 ± 0.05 (9)	1.29 ± 0.02 (3)

Note: Number of samples are shown in brackets.

* indicate significantly different mean values within columns (Fischer t-test, $p < 0.05$)

to the weighted average isotopic composition of precipitation, being $-9.66 \pm 1.09\%$ and $-69.3 \pm 7.6\%$ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$. Therefore, it was not expected to have noticeably effect of irrigation water on the isotopic composition of pore water.

The soil samples taken at greater depths had soil water isotope ratios more enriched in heavy isotopes and the d-excess decreased to values between -30.2 and -61.8% (data not shown in Figs. 3 & 4). The trend coincided with a decrease in water content and an increase in the sandy portion from 60 cm onwards, which could cause a capillary barrier effect of the underlying coarser textured soil layer. At these depths, some soil samples had water contents below $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, and resulted in unrealistic d-excess values, indicating greater inaccuracy. In their study, Wassenaar et al. (2008) reported that the direct vapor equilibration laser spectrometry method showed low accuracy in soil cores with volumetric water contents lower than $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. Also, Gralher et al. (2021) concluded that a minimum water volume of 1.47 mL was necessary to obtain accurate isotope data in bags with 1 L headspace volume. In this study, most of the samples with water content below $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ had less than 1.47 mL. Thus, the samples with volumetric water contents below $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ were discarded ($n = 27$).

The isotope ratios in all soil profiles had similar distributions with differences in values and location of the minimum winter signal. All profiles showed a decrease of $\delta^2\text{H}$ from the soil surface to a minimum in a depth between 25 and 35 cm. (Fig. 4a, b, c, d). The winter nadir in conventional tillage was found deeper compared to the rest of the tillage variants (CT: 35 cm; RT, MT and NT: 25 cm) except for one profile in MT-SI and RT-NI having minimums also situated at 35 cm depth. $\delta^2\text{H}$ profiles of CT plots had the most pronounced curve. Below 35 cm depth, some profiles indicated similar isotope values only showing slight increases (-70% to -50%), but all of them tended to attenuate with depth. This was also observed in the d-excess, which fluctuated between -14.1% and 14.6% .

With soil depth, we observe a decrease of volumetric soil water content (Fig. 4e, f, g, h), reaching very low water contents ($< 0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$) in some of the samples below 55 cm depth. NT and MT had similar θ_w trends with depth, with relatively high water content within the first 25 cm (0.12 – $0.28 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$) and a second local maximum at about 45 cm depth. Drier profiles were found in CT and RT where there was a decrease from the top, with water contents ranging from 0.07 to $0.17 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ in the upper 30 cm. The largest amount of water in the entire profile (Table 4) was found in DI-NT and DI-MT with 150 and 147 mm, while the lowest was found in NI-CT and SI-RT, with 63 and 75 mm.

3.3. Adjusted isotope profiles

A multiple regression analysis allowed to correct the bias due to enrichment in heavy isotopes produced during storage time and especially in low water content samples. The following equations were generated from the multiple regression analysis by considering the gravimetric water $\theta_g(\text{g/g})$ content and the *time* (d) between sample

preparation and isotope analysis as independent variables:

$$\Delta^{18}\text{O} = \theta_g \times 40.91 + \text{time} \times (-0.042) - 5.21 \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta^2\text{H} = \theta_g \times 199.69 + \text{time} \times (-0.301) - 21.56 \quad (7)$$

Fig. 5 shows the original and the corrected values of $\delta^2\text{H}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and d-excess for a soil profile (DI-RT). The rest of the profiles were alike. The gap widened at the low end of the profiles as the amount of water in the samples decreased, but the nadir was not affected and the minimum was located at the same depth. Thus, the original profiles were used for applying the peak-shift method to quantify water fluxes.

3.4. Water flux and balance quantification

The peak-shift method was applied to quantify the average water flux from the 30th of November 2019 until the 29th of May 2020, i.e. six months (Table 5). Water flux ranged between 3.8 mm/month in NI-CT and SI-RT, and 7.6 mm/month in DI-NT plots. The results showed a decreasing trend of water flux with increasing tillage intensity, except for RT, which had the lowest values in almost all profiles. The average water flux of NT and MT plots was 6.1 and 5.2 mm/month, while RT and CT had 4.4 mm/month. DI had the highest water flux values among the irrigation systems, with an average of 5.7 mm/month in the NT plots, followed by SI, BI and NI, which averaged 5.0, 4.7 and 4.7 mm/month, respectively.

Given that the section of the profile used for quantification was within the root zone, this flux was not assigned to potential groundwater recharge but as mobile water, which could contribute to further downward fluxes (groundwater recharge) or upward fluxes (transpiration, evaporation) after the time of sampling. The mobile soil water during *T* ranged from 23 to 46 mm. The largest amounts were found in NT plots, with 46 mm (DI) and 42 mm (SI). The variation in the mobile soil water of the NT plots was significantly higher than in the other tillage variants ($p = 2.1 \times 10^{-2}$) (Fig. 6), covering the entire range (23–46 mm). The differences were less pronounced for the irrigation systems than for the tillage variants, which showed a clear increase of mobile soil water as tillage intensity decreased; except for RT.

The soil water balance was applied to estimate cumulative evapotranspiration for each soil profile over period *T* following Eq. (3) (Table 5, Fig. 6). The total precipitation during *T* was 147 mm. The estimation of ET_0 and ET_c resulted in 352 and 350 mm, respectively; i.e. 240% of precipitation. The amounts of irrigation water used in the water balance for DI, BI and SI systems were 52, 52 and 73 mm, respectively. The resulting evapotranspiration was between 146 and 244 mm, well below the calculated potential evapotranspiration (350 mm). Calculated $\text{ET}(T)$ for the tillage and irrigation variants decreased in the order $\text{CT} > \text{RT} > \text{MT} > \text{NT}$ and $\text{SI} > \text{BI} > \text{DI} > \text{NI}$ (Fig. 6). Tillage variants did not differ significantly in evapotranspiration, whereas SI and NI had a significant effect with *p*-values of 8×10^{-3} and 3.4×10^{-5} .

4. Discussion

4.1. Water fluxes, mobile soil water and evapotranspiration

Water stable isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) and moisture content measurements in the soil profile allowed quantifying mobile soil water and evapotranspiration. The mobile soil water ranged from 23 (BI-NT, SI-RT and NI-CT) to 46 mm (DI-NT) from November 2019 to May 2020. Soil water flux ranged from 3.8 to 7.6 mm/month, and it was influenced by both tillage variant and irrigation system. If this water flux equals the potential groundwater recharge cannot be confirmed from the current study because the sampling was done during the growing period and water flux estimation was only possible within the root zone. Further, preferential flow bypassing the 90 cm and contributing to groundwater recharge cannot be excluded. If preferential flow occurred, potential

Fig. 4. Profiles of (a, b, c, d) isotope ratio of deuterium ($\delta^2\text{H}$) (‰), (e, f, g, h) soil water content (cm^3/cm^3), and (i, j, k, l) d-excess (‰) of each soil profile for each tillage variant (columns) and irrigation systems (in colors). The brown shaded area in a,b,c,d indicates the depth (Δz) where the winter nadir was identified and used to calculate the soil water flux. The winter nadirs for minimal and reduced tillage were determined at two different depth intervals, either at 20–30 cm or 30–40 cm.

Table 4
Mean soil water content (mm) up to 90 cm depth classified by tillage variant and irrigation system.

Irrigation system	Tillage variants			
	No-till	Minimal tillage	Reduced tillage	Conventional tillage
Boom irrigation	97	147	82	78
Drip irrigation	150	139	101	98
Sprinkler irrigation	139	95	75	77
No irrigation	111	126	91	63

groundwater recharge would be larger and ET smaller. Nevertheless, these monthly average water fluxes are within the expected ranges for this area if assuming that the average monthly recharge is valid for the entire year, resulting in annual water flux ranging between 45.6 and 91.2 mm/yr. A similar range (44–92 mm/yr) was given for other

locations in the eastern part of Austria estimated from water fluxes simulations using long-term soil water monitoring data (Schübl et al., 2023). In their study, Nachtnebel and Holzmann (1993) estimated a groundwater recharge of 43 mm/yr for Obersiebenbrunn using a numerical simulation model with lysimeter and field moisture data. Similarly, an annual average groundwater recharge of 54 mm was reported between 1993 and 2004 in the Marchfeld area (Fank et al., 2008), where our field site is located, using a groundwater flow model. The changes in infiltration in this area depend on meteorological conditions, soil type and conditions, type of crop and agricultural management practices (e.g. the amount of irrigation water) (Fank et al., 2008).

The cumulative evapotranspiration $ET_{(T)}$ quantified for period T ranged between 146 and 244 mm. These values represent approximately 40% and 70%, respectively, of ET_0 and ET_c calculated for the same period. In the water balance, the maximum water available to evaporate was 270 mm, corresponding to the sum of the accumulated rainfall during T (147 mm), the irrigation water applied in SI plots (73 mm), and

Fig. 5. Original and corrected values of (a) isotope ratios of deuterium (δ^2H), (b) oxygen ($\delta^{18}O$), and (c) d-excess for the soil profile under drip irrigation and reduced tillage (DI-RT). The correction was made using Eqs. 6 and 7.

Table 5
Average water flux ($q(z,T)$), mobile soil water ($D(T)$) and evapotranspiration ($ET(T)$) during period T for all the plots (T :30th November 2019–29th May 2020). The mean and standard deviation ($\bar{x} \pm s$) of each tillage variant and irrigation system are at the end of each row and column.

Parameter	Irrigation system	Tillage variant				$\bar{x} \pm s$
		No-till	Minimal tillage	Reduced tillage	Conventional tillage	
$q_{(z,t)}$ (mm/month)	Boom irrigation	3.9	6.0	4.4	4.5	4.7 ± 0.8
	Drip irrigation	7.6	5.3	4.6	5.2	5.7 ± 1.1
	Sprinkler irrigation	6.9	5.1	3.8	4.2	5.0 ± 1.2
	No irrigation	5.9	4.2	4.8	3.8	4.7 ± 0.8
	$\bar{x} \pm s$		6.1 ± 1.4	5.2 ± 0.6	4.4 ± 0.4	4.4 ± 0.5
$D(T)$ (mm)	Boom irrigation	23	36	26	27	28.0 ± 4.8
	Drip irrigation	46	32	28	31	34.3 ± 6.9
	Sprinkler irrigation	42	31	23	25	30.3 ± 7.4
	No irrigation	36	25	29	23	28.2 ± 5.0
	$\bar{x} \pm s$		36.8 ± 8.7	31.0 ± 3.9	26.5 ± 2.3	26.6 ± 3.1
$ET(T)$ (mm)	Boom irrigation	211	198	208	221	209 ± 8
	Drip irrigation	188	203	206	217	203 ± 10
	Sprinkler irrigation	214	239	232	244	232 ± 11
	No irrigation	146	157	167	173	161 ± 10
	$\bar{x} \pm s$		190 ± 27	199 ± 29	203 ± 23	214 ± 25

Fig. 6. Box and whisker plot for average values of (a, b) mobile soil water and (c, d) evapotranspiration for (a, c) tillage variants and (b, d) irrigation systems for period T, in mm. The outliers are represented with diamonds (◆). The asterisk indicates the tillage or irrigation variant with a significantly different mean compared to the group ($p < 0.05$): no-till for mobile soil water, no irrigation and sprinkler irrigation for evapotranspiration.

the water stored in the first 35 cm of the soil (50 mm). The results are average information valid for the time period T, i.e. from the end of November 2019 to the end of May 2020, and for soil depths down to 25–35 cm depth. Other time periods (i.e. summer maximum) were difficult to identify in the soil profile because there was no clear seasonality in the isotope profile below the 50 cm depth. Still, different patterns could be identified in soils under different agricultural management practices (i.e. tillage variants and irrigation systems), and the changes in hydrological processes could be compared.

4.2. Influence of management practices: Tillage and irrigation systems

The first distinction between tillage variants was observed by identifying the minimum value of the isotopic signal of precipitation in the soil profiles, i.e. the winter nadir. The winter nadir was located in all CT plots (30–40 cm depth) at a greater depth compared to the other tillage variants (20–30 cm), indicating a higher water flow velocity. Furthermore, the winter minimums in one profile in RT and MT were also found at the same depth as the CT plots. The results suggest a gradual reduction in water flow velocity as tillage intensity decreases. These findings are in line with those reported by some reviews on no-till farming, concluding that untilled fields have a lower infiltration rate than tilled fields (Skaalsveen et al., 2019; Strudley et al., 2008). This is to be expected because tillage increases macropores and soil infiltration is a function of pore size distribution (Lipiec et al., 2006). Moreover, the last tillage was done one month before the rainfall taken as the initial point for the T period, whose lightest isotope concentration was detected between 30 and 40 cm, when the soil still had large cracks through which water could have seeped in. The irrigation system did not affect water flux.

Soil water content was also affected by tillage; it decreased with increasing tillage intensity in soil profiles down to 90 cm deep. In a review study, Skaalsveen et al. (2019) concluded that the water-holding capacity of untilled soils in NW Europe was still uncertain, as it depends on soil texture, climatic conditions and farming practices carried out, such as the presence and type of cover crops. However, no-tillage

and conservation tillage practices have been shown to contribute to soil water conservation in rather dry areas where, in addition, crop residues are maintained as mulch and cover crops are used (Alvarez and Steinbach, 2009; Baumhardt and Jones, 2002; De Vita et al., 2007; Mahboubi et al., 1993; Soane et al., 2012). The experimental field of our study was located in one of the driest areas of Austria (ann. avg. P of 540 mm) and crop residues were maintained after harvest in the NT plots. The lack of mechanical intervention in the soil resulted in an increase in bulk density in the upper soil layer.

The type of irrigation system also influenced soil water content. In particular, drip irrigation resulted in higher average water volumes in the soil (122 mm up to 90 cm depth), compared to BI, SI and NI (101, 97 and 98 mm). This difference arose even with a higher volume of irrigation water applied by SI (22 mm more) compared to BI and DI. The use of drip irrigation does not necessarily increase the amount of water in the soil, as it is usually applied only to cover the water needs of the plant for transpiration and to minimize losses through evaporation and seepage (Lv et al., 2010). However, in this study, all the irrigation systems applied the irrigation water continuously one day in April and another day in May 2020 with the same amount of water, except for sprinkler irrigation. Thus, the higher soil mobile water can be explained by the lower evaporation loss of drip systems compared to sprinkler and boom irrigation systems. A reduction up to 60% in evaporation of irrigation water is assumed for DI compared to sprinkler irrigation systems (Jagermeyr et al., 2015). This is because sprinkler systems tend to increase actual evaporation, with evaporation losses up to 45%, during irrigation and shortly thereafter, mostly due to evaporation of irrigation water intercepted by the canopy (Uddin and Murphy, 2020).

The water-holding capacity of a soil and how easily water flows through it determines the amount of mobile water in the soil. Thus, a similar trend to the soil water content could be observed in soil mobile water, with a decrease in the order NT > MT > RT = CT and DI > SI > BI = NI. The lower soil mobile water in CT and RT could be caused by the larger soil surface exposed to evaporation or to the presence of preferential flow beyond 90 cm deep. In addition, the high standard

deviation observed in NT (± 8.7 mm) compared to the rest of tillage variants (± 2.3 to ± 3.9 mm) suggests a higher homogeneity of soil structure under tilled soils, also observed in other studies (Pires et al., 2017). The small differences in mobile soil water between the SI, BI and NI plots (avg. of 30 mm, 28 mm and 28 mm, respectively) suggest that irrigation water from BI and SI was mostly transpired or evaporated. The additional irrigation water in SI plots could explain the slight increase of 7% in average mobile soil water compared to BI and NI. The higher soil mobile water in DI is likely due to the reduced evaporation losses of this irrigation system compared to SI and BI, as discussed above. The higher standard deviation of SI and DI (± 7.4 and ± 6.9 mm) compared to BI and NI (± 4.9 mm) may result from the uneven water distribution that can occur in these irrigation systems due to their configuration (Allen et al., 1998; Lamm et al., 2019).

The average $ET_{(T)}$ resulting from the water balance showed a relationship with tillage intensity. This was expected, as the exposure of the soil surface to the atmospheric conditions of tilled soils is greater, potentially enhancing evaporation in the topsoil (Bronick and Lal, 2005). However, it was evident that the irrigation systems had a greater influence on evapotranspiration and, consequently, $ET_{(T)}$ in the tillage plots had large standard deviations (± 23 to ± 29 mm) compared to those shown in the irrigated plots (± 8 to ± 11 mm). For example, sprinkler irrigation had higher average $ET_{(T)}$ (232 mm) compared to BI and DI (209 and 203 mm), while the non-irrigated plots had average evapotranspiration of 161 mm. As mentioned above, additional irrigation water was applied in SI plots, which led to higher evapotranspiration. In sprinkler systems, a wide range of water losses (4–45%) has been reported in field experiments (McLean et al., 2000; Steiner et al., 1983; Uddin and Murphy, 2020; Yazar, 1984). In our study, the difference in overall evapotranspiration between SI and DI systems was 12%, and 3% if the additional irrigation water added in SI was subtracted. The amount of mobile soil water and evapotranspiration must be matched to the crop water needs to achieve a high water use efficiency and good yields. Crop demands will depend on the weather conditions and the availability of water in the soil, which is highly dependent on soil texture and structure. This will define the need for irrigation. Their effects must therefore be considered in the management of a particular field. The measurement of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^2\text{H}$ and the soil water content showed a potential for comparing water fluxes in different agricultural management practices. Although we have observed significant differences between the treatments, it is difficult to make best practice recommendations as this depends on environmental factors (e.g. physical and climatic conditions, availability of water), as well as social factors (e.g. crop used, economic benefits, sustainability goals). In future studies, the method should be used to assess soil heterogeneity and long-term effects of treatments in agricultural soils.

4.3. Isotope ratios in pore water

Soil samples from the first 10 cm of the soil are plotted below the LMWL, indicating fractionation processes due to evaporation. This can be either evaporation of soil water or evaporation during the irrigation. The isotopic composition of soil water in samples below 30 cm was closer to irrigation water and mean annual precipitation. The regression line of soil water isotopes and the LMWL meet near precipitation and irrigation water composition pointing to irrigation and average precipitation as main water source. Interestingly, no soil water samples have isotope ratios below irrigation water, while some are between irrigation water and average precipitation. In surface water, the intersection of the trend line with LMWL determines the precipitation source water. However, soil water shows a different evaporative pattern that is more strongly influenced by seasonality, and the intersection may no longer represent the source water as theoretically calculated for a soil in Vienna (Benettin et al., 2018). Here, theoretical isotope ratios in soils ranged between -10 and -3‰ for $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, which were similar but slightly lower compared to the actual measurements in the present study (-8.12 to $-$

0.67‰).

In the topsoil (down to -20 cm), d-excess had more negative values, which indicated kinetic fractionation during evaporation. High evaporation in the topsoil could create an evaporation front, i.e. a distinguished peak isotopically enriched in $\delta^2\text{H}$ below the soil surface that is caused by evaporation and defines a vapor-liquid interface (Allison et al., 1984). Once the evaporation front is overcome, water enriched in heavy isotopes is pushed to lower layers. In our soil profiles, we did not observe an evaporation front despite the low d-excess. Several studies in temperate regions identified the evaporation front within the first 0.2–0.3 m of the soil profile (Sprenger et al., 2016b; Sutanto et al., 2012). In contrast, in an agricultural area situated only 10 km west of our experimental field, Liebhard et al. (2022) identified the evaporation front within the upper 2 cm of soil. Evaporation by vapor diffusion was expected to occur in the topsoil due to the small precipitation and the increase of potential evapotranspiration during period T. In addition, soil management using tillage techniques may enhance evaporation losses, as discussed above. That explains why pore water was generally more enriched in heavy isotopes than the original source, i.e. precipitation and irrigation water.

In the lower section of the profile, soil samples discarded for low water content were associated with low d-excess. This may be due to a lower accuracy of isotope measurement using the direct liquid-vapor equilibration method in samples with very low water content. In a recent study, Vadibeler et al. (2022) concluded that the direct liquid-vapor equilibration method for porewater isotope analysis was more inaccurate in silty soils compared to kaolinite and sandy soils when the saturation level is low ($\leq 40\%$). Therefore, the adjustment using linear multiple regression analysis was made (Fig. 5). The water loss calculated was up to 3.5%. As demonstrated by Wassenaar et al. (2008), Hendry et al. (2015) and Gralher et al. (2021), storage time and water content of soil samples have an impact on the isotopic ratio, which should be considered to account for evaporative isotopic enrichment. An alternative to minimize additional fractionation due to water loss to the headspace and bag in samples with low water content would be to increase the total mass of the soil sample (Hendry et al., 2015), with a minimum water content of 1.47 mL (Gralher et al., 2021) or to use other metallized bags if an accumulation of gases is not expected in the headspace (Gralher et al., 2018). Nevertheless, the pattern of stable isotope profiles of pore water in the uppermost layers did not change after the correction, as seen in Fig. 5. Since the period was clearly identified in all the profiles, the peak-shift method can be used for water flux quantification.

4.4. Strengths and limitations of the space for time concept to quantify water flux

A major advantage of this method is the possibility of quantifying water fluxes in fields with difficult access and little data available by carrying out a single sampling campaign. Even precipitation not necessarily needs to be measured onsite because for estimating average fluxes with the peak-shift method, only minimum or maximum in the isotope distribution in precipitation from a specific location has to be known. This information can be either gained by onsite measurements, available open access data, such as the WISER portal (GNIP-IAEA) or from prediction tools (Nelson et al., 2021).

Another advantage of using soil water isotopes is that they can be traced in soils under different climates, from temperate and cold humid zones to arid and semi-arid zones (Boumaiza et al., 2021a; Chesnaux and Stumpp, 2018; Koeniger et al., 2016). The general limitation related to the climate is that it requires a pronounced stable isotope seasonality in precipitation, which depends on meteorological conditions and geographical location, e.g. inland areas have a more pronounced seasonal effect compared to coastal areas. There are also climate-specific limitations. In humid areas, the isotopic seasonal signal variations may not be observed in the soil if (1) water table is very close to the

surface or (2) the recharge is so high that new and old water mix up damping the isotopic signal in the soil profile (Chesnaux and Stumpp, 2018). In semi-arid zones, by contrast, alternating dry and rainy conditions make seasonal isotopic signals very distinguishable (Boumaiza et al., 2021a; Koeniger et al., 2016). The high evaporation rate in arid and semi-arid areas may create an evaporation front, i.e. a distinguished peak isotopically enriched in $\delta^2\text{H}$ below the soil surface (Allison et al., 1984; Diongue et al., 2023). The front could affect the seasonal peaks or nadirs in the upper layers of the soil. That is why the method must be applied only below the evaporation front (Boumaiza et al., 2021a). In arid zones with few precipitation events, distances between peaks and nadirs may be very short, which could result in mixing of soil water by diffusion, so the method could not be applied (Allison et al., 1984). In arid conditions, even if soil water isotopes are affected by evaporative fractionation, the peak-shift method may still be applicable if the pattern remains.

Depending on the climatology and location of the site, different periods can be identified from abrupt changes in the seasonal isotopic composition of precipitation events. At deeper layers, seasonal variations in the isotopic composition of precipitation are usually smoothed due to hydrodynamic dispersion (Leibundgut et al., 2009). In our study, this effect is observed in most of the profiles. However, in order to identify a period in the depth profiles, not only the isotope ratios have to be considered, but also whether the amount of precipitation is sufficient to actually trace an event, or if there is a period of non-percolation, for example, a snow cover during winter in colder regions. In their study, Boumaiza et al. (2020) identified a similar period to that of this study, from November to May, by tracking the change in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ along with the soil water content values from the time the topsoil freezes, hindering percolation, to the sampling date. Barbecot et al. (2018) also identified several periods, corresponding to spring snowmelt and autumn recharge determined in an area characterized by strong seasonality in woodland in Quebec, Canada. As a direct method that averages water fluxes for a specific time period, usually in the range of months, the peak-shift method has the potential to estimate several recharge periods if we identify consecutive peaks-nadirs, which may be optimal for tracking the high temporal variability of agricultural soils. If more dynamic processes are of interest, more sampling campaigns are needed. As an example, the impact of soil reaggregation after tilling on water fluxes, where soil structure changes within days or weeks. To detect these changes, soil core samples should be taken weekly or bi-weekly.

As for transport in the unsaturated zone, a dominant convection transport is assumed in the peak-shift method, outweighing the effect of dispersion and diffusion transport (Leibundgut et al., 2009). Hence, the applicability of water stable isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) may be limited in soils with high hydrodynamic dispersion, where the seasonal sinuosity cannot be clearly identified (Chesnaux and Stumpp, 2018). In the present study, the winter minimum is visible but pore water appears to be more enriched in heavy isotopes than that of precipitation, indicating that dispersion transport has influenced mixing with old water stored in the soil, and fractionation processes due to evaporation are of importance. Based on the distribution of dispersivities done by Vanderborght and Vereecken (2007), we assume that the dispersivity of our soil is between 2 and 6 cm under unsaturated flow conditions, which can be considered medium-low. Dispersivity can be considered if dispersion coefficients are known (Barbecot et al., 2018; Leibundgut et al., 2009; Stumpp et al., 2012). For example, Barbecot et al. (2018) used a lumped parameter dispersion model to account for dispersion. The model provided a rough estimate of the amount of groundwater recharge compared to values found in the literature despite the uncertainty. Other local site effects, like heterogeneity in the vadose zone and surface runoff/runon, may also limit water flux quantification which, however, were assumed less important for our site as all plots were on very flat terrain and homogeneous texture.

In irrigated agricultural fields, soil water isotope ratios are a combination of precipitation and irrigation water, which may hinder the

identification of periods in the profile, limiting the use of this method. This limitation can be overcome by using an end-member mixing approach to differentiate both isotopic signals when the irrigation water comes from a source with an isotopic composition different from the average local precipitation. In the study of Mahindawansa et al. (2020), irrigation water was taken from a nearby groundwater-fed reservoir that was isotopically depleted compared to rainwater. This resulted in strong variations in the isotopic composition of soil water, and the isotopic signal of water inputs was calculated from weighted values of irrigation water and rainfall. Al-Oqaïli et al. (2020) compared two irrigation systems and used the intersection between the LMWL and the trendline of water stable isotopes in soil samples as the isotopic composition of input water to calculate the fraction evaporated, assuming that irrigation water, supplied by nearby wells, had the same isotopic composition as rainwater. In our study, irrigation water came from groundwater, recharged locally, with an isotopic composition similar to the precipitation-weighted average isotopic composition, and the two signals could not be distinguished. However, irrigation water did not alter the isotopic signal in the soil profile and, therefore, did not have an impact on the application of the method.

Alternatively to the simple peak-shift approach, pore water stable isotope profiles can also be used to estimate soil hydraulic parameters in an inverse modelling framework, increasing the possibilities of assessing and predicting the behaviour of the system under changing climatic conditions or management practices (Groh et al., 2018; Sprenger et al., 2015; Stumpp et al., 2012). Here, high-resolution input data and more information about the soil water content or matric potential would be beneficial to increase the information required for inverse estimation of soil hydraulic parameters (Groh et al., 2018). The simplicity of this method compared to other methods for measuring water flux and the latest developments in measurement techniques - also in situ techniques - make it suitable for use in agricultural areas as well.

5. Summary and conclusion

In the present study, soil water content and water stable isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^2\text{H}$) of pore water in the soil profile were analyzed to quantify the soil water flux using the peak-shift method in sixteen different plots, covering all combinations of four irrigation systems and four tillage variants. The isotopic signal of precipitation was used to identify a distinctive signal in soil water and a six-month period from the end of November 2019 to May 2020 was determined. A water balance approach was used to quantify evapotranspiration and soil water flux was considered as mobile soil water.

Soil isotope profiles have shown a clear difference in percolation between the tillage variants, with the nadir of winter precipitation in CT plots reaching greater depths (35 cm) and shallower in NT plots (25 cm), with RT and MT having intermediate flow velocities. Furthermore, an increase in tillage intensity has resulted in less mobile soil water and higher evapotranspiration. As for the irrigation systems, SI and BI have led to higher evapotranspiration, while DI has contributed less to evaporation and has increased soil water content and, consequently, mobile soil water.

The peak-shift method has a great potential to quantify average water fluxes and compare the impact of management practices in agricultural fields. The differences in soil mobile water and evapotranspiration of the irrigation systems and tillage variants are consistent with the effects reported in the literature. The method averages water fluxes for a specific time period, usually in the range of months, with the potential to track several recharge periods, and is optimal for following the high temporal variability of water fluxes in agricultural soils. To study changes in water movement in the soil profile over short periods, soil core samples should be taken more frequently, e.g. weekly or bi-weekly. Nevertheless, it will be necessary to gather more information about its application in different types of soils and climatic conditions to know where it could be recommended to apply this method.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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